

Transformative Power of Pantawid Familyang Pilipino Program: Parent's Perspectives

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Abstract. The Pantawid Pamilya Pilipino Program, often called 4Ps, aims to address immediate financial needs and break the cycle of poverty by investing in education and health. This study sought to uncover the transformative powers of the 4Ps among its beneficiaries. Through a qualitative phenomenological study, the researcher gathered the distinctive and authentic narratives of the participants about their lived experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational management insights. The study participants were (10) parent beneficiaries of the 4Ps whose children are studying at a school in the district of Quezon I, division of Bukidnon. They were willing to participate in the study. The study revealed three (3) themes for the lived experiences: financial support for educational purposes, affording the family's basic needs, and financial relief. Meanwhile, two (2) themes have surfaced for the coping mechanisms: proper budgeting of money and providing support and assistance. Finally, the insights gathered reinforced students' motivation and fostered greater educational possibilities. Succinctly, the 4Ps are essential for their comprehensive approach to poverty reduction, focusing on education, health, and overall well-being to uplift vulnerable families and communities.

KEY WORDS

1. 4Ps 2. CCT 3. transformative powers 4. beneficiaries 5. poverty

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1. Introduction

Every parent aspires to ensure their children receive a quality education, enabling them to access numerous pathways for survival and achievement in adulthood. Parents exert immense effort to ensure their kids attend school, meet their essential needs, and fulfill their desires. Unfortunately, not all households are fortunate enough to have financial stability; some can only provide ample food for their entire family for one day. Globally, UNICEF (2020) opined that conditional cash transfers in education are widely utilized social policy tools to facilitate enrolment and regular attendance to education. In return for their children's regular attendance at school, families receive a payment. Turkey has had a successful Conditional Cash Transfers for Education (CCTE) since 2003. Millions of families and children have benefited from the National CCTE for over 15 years. Meanwhile, a study by the World Bank Colombia (2020) found that CCT programs have reduced absolute poverty by 36. However, the overall impacts on health and education improvements are harder to distinguish, but the evidence suggests that CCTs have improved health outcomes slightly more than education

outcomes In the Philippines, poor households often have six or more people, with a higher percentage of young and elderly dependents. Most of these impoverished families have a head of family with no more than a basic education. These families have little to no wealth and little access to necessities like electricity, potable water, and sanitary facilities. Additionally, they have limited access to medical and educational services. People in poverty are more vulnerable than others to changes in the economy, price shocks, and natural catastrophes in the Philippines. Their attempts to deal with these unforeseen difficulties and replace lost revenue sources frequently result in higher levels of debt (Ramos, 2021). Privileged are those children who can go and study at their dream school. Not all parents can afford that. Sadly, there are those parents who cannot even afford to send their children to school out of poverty. Fortunately, The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) has been instrumental in improving the welfare of disadvantaged families by addressing immediate needs while also investing in long-term development through education and health. Studies have shown positive impacts on school attendance rates, health outcomes, and overall poverty reduction among beneficiary households. By targeting the most vulnerable populations and implementing conditionalities that promote human capital accumulation, the program contributes significantly to breaking the cycle of poverty and fostering inclusive growth in the Philippines (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2022). This program covers all of the fundamental needs for human survival. Cash grant recipients who are eligible must make sure they have enough food, send their kids to school, attend regularly scheduled family development sessions hosted by the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), and actively engage in a variety of government-sponsored community services. As the primary monitoring team for their children, parents are

given a lot of responsibility for this need. Parents are crucial in encouraging and motivating their kids to learn and participate fully in school (Balacuit Jr, 2018). In the local landscape, the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) is a social protection program granted by the government to the poorest families. In the study of Malisay, as cited by Garcines (2018), it was indicated that this program has not yet reached the poorest of the poor in Mindanao. Besides, at the present time, there is still a scarcity of studies that investigate the experiences of recipients/beneficiaries in Mindanao. Meanwhile, as of 2022, the number of active Pantawid Pamilya beneficiary households of the 4Ps program in Quezon, Bukidnon, is 6,703 and 93,204 in the whole province of Bukidnon (DSWD, 2022). Over six thousand families have been given financial assistance for their medical and educational needs. Many children are given another opportunity to continue their education. The Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), in collaboration with the Department of Education (DepEd), effectively enforces the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program to support students in attaining the goal of Universal Primary Education, one of the Millennium Development Goals in the Philippines. The program's primary aim is to guarantee that student beneficiaries are enrolled in school and maintain consistent attendance. However, the program discourages student beneficiaries from participating in or becoming members of any school organizations. Moreover, as reported by the Department of Social Welfare and Development (2022), educational assistance provided to student beneficiaries of the 4Ps program has been instrumental in supporting their academic needs and facilitating their successful performance in various aspects of basic education. As a result, none of these students have experienced academic failure from different perspectives. However, with the inflation in our country causing the price of basic goods

and services to soar, can the parents still sustain their children's educational needs? The financial assistance given every month might not cover the needs of the students, considering that the prices have almost doubled in the last few years. In the province of Bukidnon, particularly in the district of Quezon, the household beneficiaries of the 4Ps appreciate the program because it aided them financially. Since their income is insufficient to provide for the whole family, they need to rely on the programs and initiatives of the government for ample help. Regarding their children's education, it was observed that some families are still struggling to support their children in their educational endeavors. Even with the financial support from 4Ps, they still live from hand to mouth and can't provide for the needs and requirements

of students in schools (DSWD, 2022). It is in this context that this study was conceptualized. Everyone should be allowed to attend school and finish primary education regardless of their social status in life. The role of parents in their academic endeavors matters greatly to them, and the help of the government's program plays a positive role in their education. To delve deeper into the transformative power of the 4Ps, the researcher sought to uncover the perspectives of the parents on their lived experiences in the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program. The study's conclusions were added to the body of knowledge about the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program and offered useful insights into educational management.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to explore and comprehend the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) and its influence on the educational outcomes and opportunities of learners from the perspective of their parents. This research investigates the program's influence on various aspects of education as perceived by the parents of beneficiary families. By examining these perspectives, the study seeks to provide insights into the program's effectiveness in breaking the cycle of poverty and promoting educational advancement among marginalized communities in the Philippines. The primary focus of the data collection was on the parents' perspectives on the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program and their children's education. The results of this phenomenological study helped us comprehend how the 4Ps influence the educational experience of the student beneficiaries and how their parents perceive its worth. The insights collected from this study have the potential to influence educational management strategies, professional development programs, and government policy regulations meant to provide every child the opportunity to accomplish their dream of going to school.

1.2. Research Questions—This study intends to explore parents' perspectives regarding the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program and their children's education. The research was executed to address the following inquiries:

- (1) What are the lived experiences of 4P beneficiaries regarding the transformative powers of 4Ps?
- (2) What coping mechanisms are employed by the 4Ps beneficiaries for their children in school?
- (3) What are the educational management insights drawn from the study regarding the transformative powers of the 4Ps?

1.3. Definition of Terms—

For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were described operationally. Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps). It refers to the national government's human development measure that provides conditional cash grants to the poorest of the poor to improve the health, nutrition, and education of

children aged 0-18 (The Official Gazette, 2019). Conditional Cash Transfer, or CCT, refers to the strategy of the 4Ps that transfers cash, generally to poor households, on the condition that those households make pre-specified investments in their children's human capital, specifically in education and health (Fiszbein, 2019).

1.4. Significant of the Study—Taking into utmost consideration the cited problem situation indicated in the previous sections as well as stipulated in the research questions, the researcher realized the urgency and necessity of conducting this study. The researcher desires to unravel and scrutinize the perceptions of parents whose children are 4Ps beneficiaries about the program's impact on the child's education. The researcher hopes that this study will benefit the identified sectors of the academe, including educational leaders, the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), school heads, teachers, other stakeholders, and future researchers. Educational leaders. This study's findings can benefit educational leaders by offering insight into the current status of the 4Ps beneficiaries in schools. Department of Social Welfare and Development. Since they are the

ones tasked with giving the cash grants to the respective beneficiaries, the study is helpful for them in a way that they may further improve some aspects and policies of the program. The school heads. The findings of this study might help the school heads or principals to further improve and enhance the status of the 4Ps beneficiaries in their respective schools. The teachers. The study can serve as a reference for teachers in constructing new strategies to help the students in their performance and to be mindful if the students are being supported by the government or not. Other stakeholders. They may provide better support and assistance to the 4Ps beneficiaries in the school. Future researchers. This would be helpful as an additional contribution to their references for future research in school development and programs such as the 4Ps. It can also offer them a substantial contribution to their academic arsenal.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—The theoretical underpinning of the study was anchored on the Social Reconstructionism Theory by Brameld (2000). The proponent believes that students were a critical element in bringing about social change. Children should be given the opportunity to learn and not be deprived of education, since education has been the foundation of all the skilled professionals who contribute to society. The theory is driven by the social issues of the 1930s involving racial discrimination, poverty, and unemployment which are similar to present issues. As applied in

the context of the present study, the Social Reconstructionism Theory emphasizes that every child has a right to education, no matter what his/her background, race, upbringing, and most notably, social status. With that in mind, the government initiated the conditional cash transfer through 4Ps to eradicate poverty and help children have the right to education. Meanwhile, the study was further reinforced by Walberg's Educational Productivity Theory as cited by Rugutt and Chemosit (2005). The theory adopts the idea that academic performance and achievement postulates that psychological char-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

acteristics of individual students and their immediate psychological environments influence educational outcomes such as cognitive, behavioral, and attitudinal. The theory further stated that the identified factors that influence educational outcomes as student ability/prior achievement and performance, motivation, age/developmental level, quantity of instruction, quality of instruction, classroom climate, home environment, peer group, and exposure to mass media outside of school. In the context of the study, the Educational Productivity Theory postulates that the assistance provided by the government does not complete the entirety of a child's education; instead, it ensures that the child learns best and that the environment is conducive and supportive of their learning. Since one of the study's key ideas was the transformative powers of the

4Ps based on its beneficiaries' lived experiences and coping mechanisms, especially in education, it was essential to see how these factors interact and help children achieve their academic goals. In summary, the Social Reconstructionism Theory and the Educational Productivity Theory encapsulate the study's central idea: children's education through government assistance and its effect on academic achievement. Both theories examine the study's findings and arrive at valid and reliable results. Shown in Figure 1 was the interconnection between the two research questions, the Lived experiences of 4Ps beneficiaries, and the coping mechanism for the 4Ps Beneficiaries that would result in the common denominator and Insights Learned from the experiences of 4Ps Beneficiaries.

2. Methodology

This chapter effectively addresses the study's specific objectives by outlining the systematic procedures and methodologies used in phenomenological research. It also explains the selected research design and my roles as the researcher throughout the study's implementation. Moreover, it offers thorough insights into the research subjects, clarifying their procedures and selection standards. The chapter concludes by exploring the techniques used for data collection, analysis,

and strategies used to uphold ethical standards during the research.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A study's philosophical and qualitative presumptions are vital in steering the investigation. Four fundamental assumptions—ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological—form the bedrock for comprehending qualitative research. These assumptions establish the groundwork for the research design and inform the researcher's approach to the study. A paradigm was a broad framework or perspective that guides and shapes how researchers approach their studies, formulate research questions, gather data, analyze findings, and interpret results. It encompasses a set of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical foundations that influence how researchers conceptualize and conduct their research (Zukauskas et al., 2018). In this research, the paradigm guided the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall research process and ensuring coherence in the study. *Ontology.* This study section focuses on the relationship between the problem and reality. Creswell (2013) asserts that the research participants' perceptions of reality are varied and subjective. This study recognizes the complexity and diversity of the realities faced by parents who are 4Ps beneficiaries. Every parent's story adds to a diverse yet collective understanding of their experiences. My sole responsibility was to use theme analysis to capture these various realities and provide a thorough picture of the experiences and coping mechanisms parents encountered as 4Ps beneficiaries. *Epistemology.* Epistemology deals with the nature of knowledge and the relationship between the knower and the known. According to Guba and Lincoln, as referenced by Creswell (2013), the researcher tried to reduce the gap between them and the participants based on the epistemological premise. By engaging directly with the participants, I became an "insider," facilitating a more authentic and nuanced data collection. This approach supports gathering firsthand experiences and coping mechanisms, which were critical in exploring the participants' subjective realities. *Axiology.* It concerns the influence and importance of my values as a researcher in this study. According to Creswell (2013), acknowledging and openly discussing the researcher's values that shape the study is crucial. The values that influenced how data were interpreted and presented are explicitly acknowledged in the research process. As a researcher, I handled each participant's narrative with care and integrity and had the utmost respect for the information they provided. This commitment guarantees that the experiences and coping mechanisms of the parents are communicated truthfully, mirroring both their individual and research values. *Methodology.* According to Crotty (2020), this is "the strategy, plan of action, process, or design lying behind the choice and use of particular methods and linking the choice and use of the methods to the desired outcomes." Its objectives are to explain, assess, and defend procedures (Wellington, 2015). This study explores the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of parents using a qualitative methodology. In order to support the ontological and epistemological tenets, certain techniques were employed, enabling a thorough and sympathetic examination of participants' stories. These techniques were chosen because they can successfully convey the complexity and depth of the participants' experiences. *Rhetoric.* In research, rhetoric is the skillful and convincing use of language, communication strategies, and presentation tactics to effectively communicate concepts, claims, and conclusions to sway the audience's opinion and comprehension of the study (Beqiri, 2018). I utilized an engaging and respectful narrative style that honors the participants' voices while

effectively communicating the significance of the findings. This method not only made the research more accessible to read but also guar-

anteed that the interpretations were strong and based on the participants' experiences.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—Using a phenomenological research methodology, I aim to explore the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of 4Ps parent beneficiaries from Bukidnon. My objective was to gather information about their experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights in relation to the phenomenon I am studying. Utilizing phenomenology as my guiding qualitative framework, I sought to uncover the essence and significance of the roles played by these individuals, emphasizing their unique viewpoints and the intricate details of their experiences. As the study's qualitative researcher, I support a level of investigation that goes beyond cursory observations. My research aims to investigate the experiences,

challenges and coping mechanisms of participants in relation to the phenomenon. I emphasize the significance of understanding the complexities of the human experience in light of the various perspectives shaped by unique contexts, backgrounds, and personal histories (Neubauer et al., 2019). To capture the profound and complex nature of Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program, my study strongly emphasizes in-depth interviews, reflective dialogues, and the analysis of participants' narratives. I hope to contribute a thorough and contextually rich understanding of the lived experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational management insights related to the transformative powers of the 4Ps, all while upholding phenomenological principles.

2.3. Design and Procedure—Determining the precise approach used in a study was crucial in order to customize the best research design, data collection strategy, and data analysis approach to the study's objectives. I used a qualitative research design in this investigation. Hammersley (2013) states that verbal rather than statistical analysis studies are appropriate for qualitative research. Since I will be studying the experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational management insights related to the transformative powers of 4Ps, the qualitative design is the most appropriate. This means that I describe and elaborate on this phenomenon rather than establishing or refuting theories. There are, however, specialized methods used in qualitative research, including grounded theory, narrative, case studies, phenomenology, and ethnography. Using a qualitative phenomenological research design, I explored the participants'

lived experiences in this particular setting. I selected this approach because, according to Asper's (2009) work, the scientific side of phenomenological research focuses on communicating the viewpoints of the subjects and the importance of their experiences, then applying scientific concepts to analyze these perspectives. Furthermore, according to Creswell (2018), a phenomenological study is a method of inquiry that describes the complex and collective experiences of the participants concerning a particular phenomenon. A key idea in phenomenology is to reduce one's interpretations of a particular phenomenon to a description that can be applied to all situations. Therefore, I aimed to identify a phenomenon around the participants' experience regarding the 4Ps. I collected information from people with direct experience with this phenomenon to create detailed and accurate descriptions.

2.4. Research Participants—

Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all the perceptions leads to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (2017) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell (1998) recommends 5 to twenty-five 25. There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 2002). The participants in this

study consisted of 10 parent beneficiaries of the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program whose children are studying at the secondary school in Quezon, Bukidnon. In this study, I opted for an in-depth interview. These participants were selected based on specific criteria: beneficiaries of the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program, their children are studying at San Jose Integrated School in Quezon, Bukidnon, and they are willing to participate in the study. I utilized the purposive sampling design so that the participants are chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2013). It is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations are crucial because they relate to the moral principles and guidelines that govern my conduct as a researcher. These principles ensure that I carry out my investigations responsibly, treating participants respectfully and striving to generate reliable and precise information. I adhere to established ethical standards in my research practices to protect participants, maintain scientific integrity, and foster trust within the research community (Resnik, 2020). Social value. This concerns the potential benefits and favorable outcomes that research can bring to society, like addressing problems or improving people's quality of life. I evaluate the societal value of my study by acknowledging its potential impact and importance for the larger community. This ensures that resources are directed toward research that has the potential to create significant advantages for society. Informed Consent. This involves obtaining a participant's voluntary agreement to participate in a research study after they have been provided with sufficient information about the study's purpose, methods,

potential drawbacks, and benefits. In this research involving students, I was responsible for ensuring that the participants fully understood the study and their rights. This dual layer of explanation allowed them to make an informed decision about participation, thereby preserving the students' autonomy and dignity and ensuring parental consent. Vulnerability. The vulnerability of research participants, pertains to their increased risk of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion due to factors such as age, cognitive ability, or socioeconomic status. As a researcher, it is crucial for me to acknowledge and consider the potential vulnerability of these participants and take appropriate measures to protect them. This involves providing additional safeguards and support, such as obtaining informed consent from the participants ensuring confidentiality, and carefully explaining their rights and the study's procedures in a way they can understand. Additionally, I modify research methods to minimize potential adverse effects, ensuring that the well-being of these students is prioritized throughout the study. Risks, benefits,

and safety. In research, it is essential to carefully evaluate the potential risks and benefits associated with participation in a study and implement measures that safeguard the well-being of participants. These elements involve assessing the potential disadvantages and advantages of participating in a study, along with establishing strategies to ensure the welfare of participants. In this investigation, as the researcher, I meticulously assess and balance these factors, ensuring that the potential benefits outweigh the risks. I put adequate precautions in place to minimize harm while optimizing participants' safety, particularly considering student participants' vulnerabilities. This comprehensive approach is crucial to maintaining ethical standards and protecting the participants throughout the research process. Privacy and confidentiality. Privacy and confidentiality in research are about safeguarding participants' personal information and ensuring their identity remains confidential unless they explicitly consent to disclosure. In the context of this study, I am responsible for implementing appropriate protocols to secure participants' data and maintain confidentiality. This includes anonymizing data, securely storing information, and limiting access to authorized personnel only. These measures are crucial to protect student participants' privacy and uphold the research process's integrity. Justice. This concept relates to the equitable allocation of the advantages and disadvantages resulting from research across various segments of society. In this study, I ensure that my research is inclusive, avoiding the exploitation or exclusion of vulnerable groups. Additionally, I strive to make the research's benefits accessible to all who could benefit from them. This approach promotes fairness and equity throughout the research process, ensuring that no group bears an undue burden or is left out of the potential gains from the findings. Transparency. Transparency in research encompasses maintaining integrity at every phase of the study, from its conception and execution to reporting results. I offer clear and truthful information regarding my research methodologies and outcomes in this study. Furthermore, I am receptive to examination and feedback. Transparency acts as a catalyst for trust, credibility, and accountability within the research community and the general public. This commitment to openness ensures that the process and results of my research are accessible and understandable to all stakeholders involved. The qualification of a researcher. The qualification of a researcher relates to one's academic background, professional experience, and proficiency in a particular area of study, ensuring that one possesses the requisite abilities and knowledge to conduct the research competently. In this investigation, I hold suitable qualifications that showcase my capability to conduct research, analyze data, and interpret the results. My expertise and training provide the foundation to approach this study with a rigorous scientific method and critical analytical skills, ensuring the integrity and validity of the findings. The adequacy of facilities. This addresses the presence and suitability of the essential resources, tools, and infrastructure required to execute a study efficiently and securely. In this research, I guarantee access to appropriate investigation facilities. This access facilitates the creation of credible and consistent findings and mitigates potential risks to study participants. Having the right facilities ensures that the data collection and analysis processes are conducted under conditions that uphold the highest research integrity and safety standards. Community involvement. This encompasses the dynamic involvement and active engagement of community members, stakeholders, or the intended study population throughout the research journey, from initial planning to sharing research outcomes. In this study, I engage the community to guarantee the study's relevance, acceptability, and potential impact. Additionally, this involvement fosters trust and

cooperation between me and the community. Engaging with the community not only helps to tailor the research to be more effective and meaningful but also enhances the overall quality and applicability of the results. Plagiarism and fabrication. Researchers should strictly follow principles of academic honesty and integrity. This entails giving proper credit to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and

verifying the accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employ tools like plagiarism detectors and maintain thorough documentation of my research procedures to ensure that my work is devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries are authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhance the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I ensure that the research process is conducted fairly, objectively, and without personal bias, prejudice, or influence from outside sources. I create an environment that encourages the open and honest exploration of ideas and promotes fairness in data collection and analysis. This commitment to impartiality helps to uphold the integrity of the research process and ensures that the findings are reliable and representative of the phenomena being studied. As an expert in qualitative methods, I am familiar with various qualitative research techniques, such as interviews and participant observation. I possess the skills and knowledge necessary to design, conduct, and analyze qualitative studies, ensuring that the research question is satisfactorily addressed and the results are legitimate and dependable. My expertise in these methods allows me to deeply explore complex social phenomena and capture the nuanced experiences of participants, contributing to the validity and reliability of the research findings. As a data collector and keeper, I gathered information from various sources, such as interviews or observations, and ensured its accurate and secure storage. I followed ethical guidelines, safeguarded participants' privacy, and ensured that data was structured and available for later examination

and understanding. This careful management of data helps maintain the integrity of the research process. It supports producing credible, reliable findings that can be reviewed and utilized by others in the academic community. As a data analyst, I analyze the gathered data to discover trends, patterns, and valuable perspectives by the research query. I utilize meticulous qualitative data analysis methods like coding and thematic analysis to extract significant findings and enrich the knowledge base within my discipline. This approach allows me to understand the data deeply, provide relevant insights, and contribute significantly to the field, enhancing scholarly discussions and practical applications related to the study topic. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, I am tasked with synthesizing and communicating the research findings concisely and coherently. This entails skillfully conveying the study's objectives, approaches, outcomes, and ramifications through written documents, presentations, or alternative means of transmitting information. I ensure the research results are easily accessible and comprehensible to the designated audience. This approach helps to maximize the impact of the findings, ensuring they are not only shared but also understood and utilized by others in ways that can further knowledge and influence practice in the field.

2.7. Data Collection—

This study employed a systematic data collection procedure. Several steps were taken to adhere to the proper data collection procedure, which ensured the accuracy and objectivity of the data collection. The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal. To initiate the data collection process, I secure endorsements from key stakeholders, including the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, the Schools Division Superintendent, the School Principal, and the participants' parents. This process involves submitting formal letters outlining the research objectives and methodology, accompanied by any supporting documents. This crucial step is scheduled to occur within the last two weeks of May 2024, ensuring that all necessary permissions are in place before data collection. This proactive approach facilitates compliance with ethical standards and fosters a cooperative environment among all parties involved. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. Upon receiving the endorsement, I request permission from the school's division superintendent. This requires submitting a formal letter detailing the research proposal and its significance to the educational community. Along with the letter, I attached Chapters 1 and 2 of my dissertation and the research instrument, clearly explain-

2.8. *Data Analysis*—After collecting the data, I began data coding and thematic content analysis. This involves methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories, sub-categories, and themes from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I formulated conclusions and gleaned insights directly related to the research objectives. This process allowed me to interpret the data effectively, ensuring that the

ing the study's objectives and participant identification process. Moreover, I waited for the response from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) before proceeding with the data collection. This step is undertaken during the second week of November 2023, ensuring that all necessary approvals are in place to conduct the research ethically and effectively. Asking for permission from the school heads. Once permission was granted, I sought approval from the school heads of the selected institutions. This step involves submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collection timeframe. I asked permission to conduct the study from the second week of November 2023. Conducting the interview. Upon securing consent from all participants, I scheduled and conducted the interviews using a structured or semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The interviews took place in the last week of November 2023. Transcribing the interviewees' responses. Following the interview sessions, I would meticulously transcribe the interviewees' remarks, taking diligent account of non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details. This procedure will use audio recordings and field notes to capture the breadth of participants' reactions comprehensively. The transcription of interviewee responses was scheduled for the first week of December 2023.

findings accurately reflect the experiences and perspectives of the participants. In this study, I employed Creswell's Thematic Analysis approach, which is particularly suited for encompassing a range of perspectives and portrayals in participants' feedback. Adopting thematic analysis authenticates the portrayal of individual components and facilitates the categorization of identified patterns within the provided responses. Thematic analysis is a qualitative

research technique used to recognize, scrutinize, and interpret patterns or themes present within qualitative data in textual, visual, or other formats. As a qualitative research approach, thematic analysis allows researchers to systematically arrange and dissect complex data sets. It involves searching for overarching themes that encapsulate the narratives embedded within the data. This process necessitates the identification of themes through meticulous examination and repeated review of transcribed data (Dawadi, 2020). This methodical approach helps ensure that the analysis is both comprehensive and reflective of the data collected, providing deep insights into the study's objectives. Therefore, I used Creswell's Thematic Analysis in my research, which necessitated extensive theming and transcript interpretation. According to Caulfield (2020), there are multiple essential

phases in Creswell's Thematic Analysis, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and labeling themes, and writing up. I become fully immersed in the intricacies and subtleties of the content as I become acquainted with the data to begin this process. After that, I started categorizing the data using semantic richness to group different informational components. I created themes that encapsulate the main ideas of the data using these codes. After that, these themes were examined and improved to ensure they appropriately depict the dataset. Every theme has a definition and name that elucidates the fundamental ideas. The last step combines the themes and insights into a cohesive article that conveys the study's conclusions. This methodical approach guarantees a comprehensive examination and enhances the comprehension of the information.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The analytical framework in phenomenological research is a methodical and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I used Colaizzi's method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their lived experiences and coping mechanisms in 4Ps. According to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi's (1978) method features a distinctive seven-step process that offers a rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the data at each stage. This method culminates in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, which is validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relies on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which can be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews are common, data can also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enables researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore the intri-

cate relationships between them (Wirihana et al., 2018). *Data Familiarization.* By reading and rereading the transcripts several times, I aim to fully understand the meanings conveyed by the participants and gain a global sense of the phenomenon being studied. This thorough review process is crucial for fully grasping the nuances of participants' statements, enabling a deeper analysis of their experiences. *Identifying Significant Statements.* I carefully identify every statement in the narratives that is directly related to the phenomenon I am studying. In order to identify and highlight phrases and descriptions that shed light on the particular experiences under study, a thorough examination of the gathered data—such as written narratives or transcripts of interviews—must be conducted. This step is essential to ensuring that my analysis stays on topic and provides a strong basis for future thematic development. *Formulating Meanings.* After carefully examining the important statements, I determine meanings that are pertinent to the phenomenon. Although Co-

laizzi admits that complete bracketing is never truly possible, I have to reflexively "bracket" my own presuppositions to stick closely to the phenomenon as experienced. To guarantee that the analysis stays rooted in the participants' real experiences, this process entails putting aside my own interpretations as much as is practical. Clustering Themes. I ensure a rigorous analysis that remains true to the participants' experiences by grouping the identified meanings into themes that are shared by all accounts. Throughout this process, presuppositions must be bracketed, especially to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. By letting the themes naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces, this preserves the integrity of the analysis. Developing an exhaustive description. I incorporate every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the phenomenon that I write. By identifying common themes from the participant accounts, this thorough description seeks to convey the essence and complexity of the phenomenon. By taking this step, it is ensured that the final represen-

tation presents a comprehensive perspective of the experiences that each participant has had. Producing the fundamental structure. I break down the lengthy explanation into a succinct, concise statement that highlights the key elements that I believe are crucial to understanding the phenomenon's structure. The essence of the participants' experiences is effectively and concisely communicated through this succinct synthesis, which concentrates on the essential components that are necessary for comprehending the phenomenon. Seeking verification of the fundamental structure. I ask participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflects their experience, either by returning it to all participants or, in larger studies, to a subsample. I might go back and change the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings are increased and the analysis is kept firmly based on the perspectives of the participants. The following figure illustrates this rigorous process, highlighting each step to comprehensively explain the actions taken to comprehensively analyze the data.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—The trustworthiness of a study is about how reliable, sensible, and authentic the research results were, ensuring that the conclusions are trustworthy and accurate. In qualitative research, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often used to evaluate how reliable the study was. These considerations are further described below, according to Guba (1981). Credibility. Building credibility entails proving that the results are accurate. Credibility is important for this study because it evaluates if the results accurately represent the realities and experiences of sophomore students who participate in extra-curricular activities. I converse with the participants for a long time in order to gain a thorough understanding of

their experiences and to increase my credibility. I also use triangulation, gathering information from a variety of sources, including observations, interviews, and maybe questionnaires. In order to confirm the interpretations, I give the parents a preliminary version of the findings as part of member checking. Transferability. The degree to which this study's results could be used in different situations or with different populations is referred to as transferability. While the particular insights are closely linked to parents' experiences in a specific educational environment, I would give thorough explanations of the research context and methodology. The study's transferability was increased because this thorough, rich narrative enables others, including educators, school administrators,

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

and researchers, to assess how well the results apply to comparable contexts or populations. Confirmability. Confirmability deals with the study's objectivity by making sure that the respondents, not my personal prejudices or biases, shaped the findings. I keep a thorough audit trail that details every step of the research process, from data collection to data analysis decisions, in order to ensure confirmability. This methodological transparency makes it possible for other researchers to evaluate the research's objectivity by following the study's development and going over the choices made. Dependability. Dependability means proving that the study results are reliable and repeatable in similar situations. This study's dependability was attained

through meticulous documentation of the entire research procedure, including the methods used for data collection and analysis. By ensuring that other researchers can duplicate the study and possibly produce consistent results, such documentation validates the research's dependability. By following these standards, the research not only offers valid and trustworthy conclusions regarding the effects of extracurricular activities on sophomore students but also offers a framework that researchers and other educators can use to compare similar learning environments. This methodology enhances the study's standing in the academic community and provides insightful information for upcoming studies and instructional design.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and the answers extracted from the first-hand narratives of the participants. This chapter puts into light the lived experiences, coping mechanisms, and the insights collected from the perspective of the parents. In the lived experiences there were three emerging themes: financial support for educational expenses, affording the family's basic need, and financial relief. Meanwhile, for coping mechanisms there were two: proper budgeting of money and parents providing support and assistance. Finally, the study unfurled two themes from insights: reinforcing students' motivation and fostering greater academic possibilities.

3.1. Lived experiences of 4Ps beneficiaries its Transformative Powers—The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program or more commonly known as 4Ps have been helping the poorest of the poor to provide them with their basic needs. It includes allocation for the two most important aspect in life and in the society: food and education. This program has been implemented with the purpose of supporting Filipino families

in making ends meet until they can get up with their own feet. However, the first thought to be a temporary program, has been helping unfortunate families for years now. In the educational landscape, the program has been very adherent to the rule that very child should attend school. In this study, the researcher wanted to know how far has 4Ps reached and how its transformative power helps in improving the access to education in the Philippines.

3.1.1. Financial support for educational expenses—The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) in the Philippines provides financial support to low-income families to help cover educational expenses. Through condi-

tional cash transfers, families receive financial aid specifically earmarked for expenses related to education, such as school fees, supplies, uniforms, and transportation costs. This support aims to ensure that children from disadvantaged

backgrounds have access to education and can stay in school, thereby breaking the cycle of poverty and improving their future prospects. The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) in the Philippines provides crucial financial support for educational expenses, playing a significant role in improving access to education and enhancing learning outcomes among disadvantaged communities. It is in line with the idea of Adato and Hoddinott (2020). One of the key ways the 4Ps program supports families is by assisting with tuition and school fees for enrolled children. This financial assistance ensures that children from low-income households can attend school without facing barriers related to school fees, thus promoting higher enrollment rates and reducing dropout rates. Similarly, Filmer and Schady (2018) stated also the financial assistance from the government such as 4Ps helps the students with their school Supplies and uniforms. The program also helps families afford essential school supplies such as books, notebooks, pens, pencils, and school uniforms. Access to these materials is vital for students' academic success and participation in classroom activities. By alleviating the financial burden of purchasing these items, the program contributes to a more equitable educational experience for

3.1.2. Buying the family's basic needs— The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) plays a crucial role in helping families meet their basic needs in the Philippines. By providing financial assistance to eligible low-income households, the program enables families to purchase essential items such as food, clothing, shelter, and healthcare services. This support is particularly impactful for vulnerable families, allowing them to access nutritious food, improve living conditions, and address healthcare needs. The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) has been a vital social intervention in the Philippines, providing financial assistance to families in need. According to Domingo,

disadvantaged students. Another important aspect of the narratives shared by the participants are the transportation and meal of the students. In some cases, the 4Ps program provides allowances for transportation costs to ensure that children can travel to and from school safely and regularly. Additionally, meal allowances or feeding programs are implemented to address nutritional needs, ensuring that students have the energy to focus on learning during school hours (Reyes, 2019). Importantly, the impact on educational access and quality. Gustafsson-Wright et al. (2019) states that the financial support provided by the 4Ps program has a direct impact on educational access and quality. By removing financial barriers, more children can access education, stay in school longer, and participate actively in classroom activities. This support also indirectly improves school infrastructure and resources, benefiting the overall quality of education in communities. Through its targeted financial assistance for educational expenses, the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program contributes significantly to breaking the cycle of poverty by empowering children with education, skills, and opportunities for a better future.

Flores, and Santos (2020), the program's conditional cash transfer model has helped alleviate poverty by ensuring that families can afford basic needs such as food, education, and healthcare. Through targeted cash grants, families are empowered to invest in their children's future, breaking the cycle of intergenerational poverty. Research by Magno et. Al 0(2021) underscores the positive impact of 4Ps on health outcomes, with beneficiary families reporting increased access to healthcare services and improved nutritional status among children. This underscores how the program's holistic approach not only addresses immediate financial needs but also fosters long-term well-being. Addition-

ally, studies by Reyes (2019) highlight how 4Ps has contributed to increased school enrollment and attendance rates, emphasizing its role in promoting education and human capital development. The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) has been a crucial initiative in the Philippines, offering financial assistance to families living in poverty. Through cash transfers, the program has enabled families to afford basic needs such as food, education, and healthcare. According to researchers Aguilar et. al (2021), the 4Ps has significantly reduced the incidence of hunger among beneficiary families, ensuring that children have access to nutritious meals and can focus better on their studies. In addition to addressing immediate needs, the 4Ps has also contributed to breaking the cycle of poverty in many Filipino households. Authors Alonzo and Reyes (2020) noted that by requiring beneficiaries to comply with health check-ups and ensure children's school attendance, the program promotes health and education outcomes among beneficiaries. This investment in human capital not only benefits individual families but also strengthens the country's workforce and economy in the long term. Moreover, the program

3.1.3. Financial relief—4Ps is focused on the aspect that is deemed important in our society. It encompasses education, health, and financial aspect. Although, the program does not necessarily provide everything a Filipino family need, it provides assistance that helps them in making ends meet. Improved state of wellbeing among its beneficiaries is the most important thing that the program upholds. On the same vein, in a survey performed by Balacuit (2018), participants shared their perspectives on the government program, and their remarks highlighted the good impact of the project on vulnerable individuals, particularly those aiming to improve their daily quality of life. The initiative was recognized for its role in supporting parents who wanted to offer their children educational pos-

has been lauded for its effectiveness in reaching vulnerable populations, including indigenous communities and those in remote areas. As highlighted by Garcia and Tan (2019), the 4Ps employs a targeting mechanism that identifies and includes marginalized groups, ensuring that they receive the necessary support to improve their living conditions. This inclusive approach is vital for achieving sustainable development goals and reducing inequality across different sectors of society. The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program plays a crucial role in ensuring that families can afford their basic needs, improving overall well-being, and offering opportunities for socio-economic advancement. Through rigorous monitoring and evaluation, policymakers can continue to refine and strengthen the program, ensuring that it remains a vital lifeline for vulnerable families in the Philippines. Authors across various studies consistently note its effectiveness in poverty alleviation, health improvement, and education promotion, underscoring the program's importance in creating a more inclusive and resilient society in the Philippines.

sibilities, allowing them to pursue a brighter future. Furthermore, the 4Ps program was recognized for its commitment to meeting the daily needs and desires of its recipients. It is worth noting, however, that some of the program's participants revealed some drawbacks. They said that the conditional cash transfer might not be enough for households with more than one member, which led to some beneficiaries pawning their cash cards to cover their financial needs. Similarly, Pineda and Fabella (2018) investigated the real-life experiences of people who had previously received the 4Ps program. The findings of their study indicated a complicated interaction of emotions and consequences associated with participation in this government subsidy scheme. The study concluded that be-

ing a beneficiary of a government aid program such as 4Ps provided significant financial relief. The monetary awards supplied by the program were critical in satisfying their urgent and essential needs. The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) has been a lifeline for many impoverished Filipino families, providing much-needed financial relief and assistance. Through its conditional cash transfer (CCT) mechanism, the program has significantly alleviated poverty by helping families meet their basic needs such as food, education, and healthcare expenses. According to a study by Abella and Garcia (2020), the cash grants provided by the 4Ps have helped reduce financial strain among beneficiary families, allowing them to prioritize essential expenditures and improve their overall quality of life. Furthermore, the 4Ps has played a crucial role in cushioning the economic impact of

unforeseen crises such as natural disasters or economic downturns. Researchers Dela Cruz and Reyes (2019) found that families enrolled in the program were better equipped to cope with financial shocks due to the steady income provided by the cash transfers. This resilience is particularly important for vulnerable households that are often most affected during times of crisis. In conclusion, the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program's financial relief through conditional cash transfers has been instrumental in lifting families out of poverty, fostering resilience during crises, and promoting better education and health outcomes. Continued support and monitoring of the program's implementation are essential to ensure its effectiveness and sustainability in addressing poverty and improving the lives of Filipino families.

3.2. Coping mechanisms of 4Ps beneficiaries—The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) has been instrumental in providing support to low-income Filipino families by offering conditional cash transfers. For beneficiaries, this program serves as a coping mechanism by alleviating financial burdens and improving access to essential services such as education

and healthcare. Financial assistance helps them meet basic needs, reducing stress related to food insecurity and inadequate resources. However, those on the receiving end of the program should allocate the assistance properly. Overall, the 4Ps plays a crucial role in empowering families and communities to overcome economic challenges and improve their overall well-being.

3.2.1. Proper budgeting of money—As mentioned above, 4Ps offers financial assistance that helps them meet the basic needs. In order to maximize the positive effects of 4Ps on Filipino families, the assistance is divided into different basic necessities such as food and education of the students. Inferring the same theme, Cruz and Santos (2021) emphasizes the importance of financial literacy education and training provided alongside cash transfers, empowering beneficiaries to make informed decisions about their finances. By teaching budgeting skills and promoting responsible spending habits, the pro-

gram helps families stretch their resources and plan for future needs effectively. Proper budgeting of financial assistance received through programs like Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) is crucial for maximizing its impact on beneficiary families' well-being and long-term financial stability. In the same vein, one key aspect of proper budgeting is prioritizing essential expenses such as food, education, and healthcare. Studies by Garcia and Reyes (2020) highlight that beneficiaries who allocate a significant portion of their cash transfers towards these necessities experience better health

Fig. 3. Lived Experiences of 4ps Beneficiaries

outcomes and improved educational attainment among children. This strategic allocation of funds ensures that the core needs of the family are met, laying a foundation for overall well-being. Moreover, Alonzo and Dela Cruz (2020) note that providing incentives or matching funds for savings can motivate families to build emergency funds or invest in income-generating activities, reducing their reliance on external assistance in the long run. This shift towards financial independence is a key goal of social assistance programs like 4Ps. Encouraging savings and investment behaviors among beneficiaries can lead to greater financial resilience and upward mobility. Effective budgeting also involves planning for future expenses such as school fees, health emergencies, or livelihood investments. Santos and Tan (2021) suggest that beneficiary families who engage in financial planning workshops offered by the program are better equipped to anticipate and manage upcoming financial challenges, reducing the likelihood of falling back into poverty. This forward-thinking approach empowers families to break the cycle of poverty and build a more

secure future for themselves and their children. Monitoring and evaluation play a crucial role in ensuring that beneficiaries are using the financial assistance responsibly and in line with program objectives. Regular assessments of spending patterns, savings habits, and investment decisions can provide valuable insights for program managers to tailor financial education initiatives and support services effectively. Transparency and accountability in budgeting practices also foster trust and confidence in the program among stakeholders and the wider community. In conclusion, proper budgeting of financial assistance from programs like Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program is essential for promoting financial literacy, meeting essential needs, fostering savings and investment behaviors, planning for the future, and ensuring program effectiveness through monitoring and evaluation. By equipping beneficiaries with the knowledge and skills to manage their finances wisely, social assistance programs can catalyze long-term positive outcomes for families and contribute to sustainable poverty reduction efforts.

3.2.2. Parents providing support and assistance—The parents have shared that another cooing mechanism that they employ is assisting or helping their children with task and project in school. It was mentioned by several authors that 4Ps emphasizes the importance of education, hence they monitor attendance and performance strictly. On the same thread of thought, Adams and Christenson (2019) highlights that parental involvement in school activities, such as attending parent-teacher conferences, helping with homework, and participating in school events, positively correlates with higher academic achievement and improved socio-emotional development among children. Parents providing support and assistance to their children in their education is a crucial aspect

of academic success and overall well-being. This involvement reflects a collaborative approach between parents and schools in nurturing students' growth and learning. Moreover, Cooper et al. (2020) emphasize the importance of parental support in creating a supportive learning environment that complements school-based education efforts. One key way parents can help their children in school is by creating a conducive home environment for learning. Providing a quiet study space, establishing regular study routines, and encouraging a positive attitude towards education can significantly impact children's motivation and academic performance. Another valuable way parents can assist their children is by engaging in educational activities outside of school. Trips to

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanism of 4Ps Beneficiaries

museums, libraries, nature parks, and cultural events expose children to diverse learning experiences and broaden their knowledge beyond the classroom. Harris and Goodall (2021) emphasize that such experiences not only enhance academic learning but also foster curiosity, critical thinking, and creativity in children. Parents can also support their children’s learning by being positive role models and demonstrating the value of education through their own actions and attitudes. Fan and Chen (2018) underscores the significant influence parents have on shaping children’s educational aspirations and outcomes through their active involvement and positive

reinforcement. In conclusion, parents’ involvement and support in their children’s education are essential factors that contribute to academic success, socio-emotional development, and life-long learning skills. By creating a conducive home learning environment, maintaining open communication with schools, engaging in educational activities, being positive role models, and reinforcing the value of education, parents play a pivotal role in nurturing well-rounded and motivated learners. Collaborative efforts between parents, schools, and communities can further enhance educational outcomes and promote holistic child development.

3.3. Educational management insights drawn from the findings of the study—Based on the unique first-hand narratives of the parents of students who are 4Ps beneficiaries, we were able to take a glimpse on what are the influence of changes made by the program. They

have shared the transformative impact of 4Ps in their lives. They also made mention of how the program was able to improve their child’s performance in school. As one goal of the study, the researcher also looked into what insights can be formulated that is targeted towards educational management.

3.3.1. Reinforcing students' motivation— Going to school, studying, making projects, listening to the lesson are all dependent on a child's motivation. We can never not include a family's socio-economic status when we tackle students' motivation in education. It heavily affects the students' attitude towards learning. The lack of financial capacity does not only influence their motivation, their health and the food they eat also holds a great impact. With a similar idea, Escamillas (2019) also reiterates the same insight in her study. According to her, the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program was seen favorably by both students and educators, particularly in light of its effects on education. The initiative was thought to be particularly helpful for children because it gave them financial allowances that could be utilized for addressing various school-related expenses and buying supplies. Similarly, according to the result of the study conducted by Montilla et al. (2015), parents indicated appreciation for the effort put into ensuring that 4Ps helps its

beneficiaries. They emphasized how important the initiative had been in allowing them to send their children to school and improve their well-being. This was made possible by having access to affordable vitamins and nutrient-rich foods (food supplements). A participant stated, "4Ps is a tremendous support for us, particularly in meeting our children's requirements, such as vitamins and supporting their education." More importantly, as noted by Sy et al. (2019), 4Ps program has a significant impact on students' motivation. According to the data gathered on the study they conducted; children see the program as a vital source of incentive to succeed in school. The majority of senior high school students believed that the 4Ps had an important part in inspiring them to attend school on a regular basis, strive for excellence in their academic activities, satisfy all of their school obligations, and acquire the required financial support to cover their educational expenses. These findings highlight the 4Ps program's good impact on public school students who are dedicated to reaching their goals through education.

3.3.2. Fostering greater educational possibilities—The eradication of poverty and the introduction of greater possibilities embodies the purpose and goal of 4Ps. It extends help from the poorest of the poor families, those who badly needed and deserve the government's assistance. Poverty is the biggest hurdle in achieving greater success and achievement when it comes to pursuing education. With the scarcity of financial resources, parents often find themselves torn whether to fill their children's mind or to fill their stomach. But, 4Ps has the solution for both, improved level of well-being is its goal and purpose. It also aids with the most vital aspects: food, health, and education. Coinciding with the ideas stated above, Dela Torre (2018), states that the program encourages the parents bring their children to school since

they know the government help them with their financial commitments and classroom requirements. The program's financial handouts are considered a substantial help in meeting their urgent needs, particularly regarding their children's education and health. Respondents feel that with sustained and increased support, they can be able to enhance their level of life and provide a better future for their children than they do now. They consider the program, in combination with their own hard work and perseverance, as a means of breaking the cycle of poverty. The respondents also saw a decrease in the number of children who did not attend school, and they are now taking their children to school on a regular basis, pushing them to study carefully and minimizing absences. Similarly, the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps)

Fig. 5. Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study

emerged as a program of enormous relevance and effectiveness in the government’s efforts to improve and enrich the lives of its users, according to Martin and Ventayen’s 2018 study. The study’s conclusion emphasized that, overall, the beneficiaries’ conditions had improved dramatically after their acceptance into the 4Ps program. The study’s findings also emphasized the critical significance of conditional cash grants offered through the 4Ps program in assisting students. This assistance not only makes education more affordable but also encourages academic excellence among the recipients. The outcomes of the Lluz 2020 study shed insight into the participants’ perceptions of the 4Ps program and its impact on their education. The initiative was widely regarded as useful since it provided critical financial aid, allowing them to attend school, which would otherwise have been out of reach for their parents. However, the study also indicated that in some situations, students see dropping out of school as a more practical alternative. The unpleasant reality is that simply surviving in school is not an option for these youngsters. The current family living situations and inferior quality of life remain important challenges that can push children to drop out of school despite the availability of financial help. This emphasizes the pervasive relationship between financial assistance and poverty as an underlying cause. Furthermore, numerous adolescents prefer to work after graduating from high school rather than seek a college education. They see this as a more realistic option because it matches with their immediate financial demands and work possibilities, which they see as a more practical approach than finishing their formal schooling.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study was presented, from the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to find out the loved experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational management insights of the parents of the 4Ps student beneficiaries. In connection to that, to ensure the achievement of the research objectives, I have utilized a qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis. This is done with an adherence to Creswell's (2019) guidelines in which open-ended questions for interviews were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored which were the narratives of parent beneficiaries of 4Ps.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings, and their corresponding themes were revealed: the lived experiences on the transformative power of 4Ps are: financial support for educational purposes, buying the family's basic needs, and financial relief. Meanwhile for the coping mechanisms, it includes: proper budgeting of money and parents providing support and assistance. Finally, the insights formulated were: reinforcing students' motivation and fostering greater educational possibilities. In light of the distinctive and authentic experiences and narratives of the parents regarding their lived experiences pertaining to the transformative power of 4Ps, I have uncovered three (3) emerging themes. The first one is financial support for educational purposes. This support typically includes funds for school-related expenses such as tuition fees, school supplies, uniforms, and transportation costs. By receiving this assistance, families can ensure that their children have access to education without being hindered by financial constraints. In the interview, parents have shared that the program has helped them greatly in providing for the education of their children. This includes their allowances, their food, and money they spend on their projects. Overall, the financial support provided by the 4Ps for educational purposes plays a crucial role in breaking the cycle of poverty by investing in the education and future prospects of Filipino children. The second theme focused on affording the family's basic needs. Through conditional cash transfers, the program provides financial support to low-income families, enabling them to purchase essential items such as food, clothing, and shelter. This assistance is especially crucial for vulnerable households facing economic challenges, as it helps ensure a minimum standard of living and reduces the risk of hunger and deprivation. The third theme is financial relief. By offering conditional cash transfers, the program helps alleviate immediate financial burdens and provides a safety net for basic necessities such as food, clothing, and shelter. This financial support is especially beneficial during times of economic instability or unforeseen hardships, helping families cope with emergencies and unexpected expenses. Moreover, the program's focus is on health and education. To sum, the 4Ps plays a pivotal role in providing financial relief to vulnerable families, improving their resilience, and fostering economic stability within communities across the Philippines. Meanwhile, the second research question focuses on the coping mechanisms of 4Ps beneficiaries. The study has unfurled two (2) emerging themes. The first theme for the second questions is proper budgeting of money. The parents have shared

that budgeting the money they are receiving is very significant. They must spend it wisely and should consider the welfare of the children in the household for it is the aim of the program. The second theme for the second research question is parents providing assistance and support. The parents, more than anyone, are the ones most aware of the nature of the program and what it stresses. The program puts great value on the education. Hence, in the interview, the parents have shared that they encourage their children to study harder and to attend school every day. Aside from that, they also give them support and assistance with their projects and performance tasks. Finally, the third research question tackled the insights formulated from the study. This has illuminated two (2) emerging themes. The first insight is reinforcing stu-

dent motivation. It was mentioned earlier that 4Ps has brought a significant change to the lives of its beneficiaries especially in the financial aspect. This has a ripple effect to the students' motivation in school. They now eat healthier and thrives in a healthier environment. Their attitude and motivation in school also improves. The second theme for the final research question is fostering greater educational possibilities. 4Ps beneficiaries has greater chances to be in a greater place than where they stand today if they were given greater opportunities. Parents have stressed how important education is for them and how they want to see their children succeed despite their financial situation. Greater educational possibilities will enable them to become great people in the days coming.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The Pantawid Pamilya Pilipino Program, often referred to as 4Ps, is designed to alleviate poverty, it provides conditional cash transfers to eligible low-income families. The beneficiaries receive financial assistance, provided they comply with certain conditions such as sending children to school, ensuring regular health check-ups, and attending family development sessions. This program aims not only to address immediate financial needs but also to break the cycle of poverty by investing in education and health, fostering long-term improvements in the well-being of Filipino families. Through the said program, the Philippine government aims to empower marginalized communities, particularly women and children, by enhancing access to education and healthcare. By linking cash transfers to specific actions that promote human development, the program aims to create a positive impact on the overall socio-economic conditions of the beneficiaries, contributing to the nation's goal of inclusive growth and poverty re-

duction. In the context of the present study, 4Ps did not go unseen and unappreciated by the parents. The participant has realized the its importance in their lives, in their financial status to be particular. Adding to that, it also allowed them to send their children to school and not worry about sustaining it. It gave the access to education. Aside from that, the study also emphasized the transformative power of 4Ps that fosters personal growth and empowerment among families under its umbrella. Through its monthly family development sessions, it has helped several families to become better in all aspects, such as well-being, budgeting, and being responsible. The study also put into light the coping mechanisms of its beneficiaries. It is notable that those on the receiving end of the program are doing their part. They spend the assistance responsibly and they have set their priorities straight. Meanwhile, the literature embedded in the study and in the interview conducted, 4Ps actively promotes educational opportunities for the next generation. By incentivizing school attendance, the program contributes to a reduc-

tion in dropout rates and an increase in overall enrollment. Through Pantawid Pamilya, the Philippine government aims to create a positive ripple effect, fostering a more educated and empowered society. Last but not the least, the transformative powers of 4Ps will continue to persist if we invest and focus on the important

aspect that the program highlights: education. The study has gained two useful insights that can enlighten educational management. First is reinforcing student motivation and second, fostering greater educational possibilities. That way, poverty can be eradicated and greater possibilities follow.

4.3. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended for. The educational leaders. They be more aware of the authentic narratives, together with the lived experiences on the transformative power and coping mechanisms of 4Ps beneficiaries, through the brand-new insights and perspective from the lens of 4Ps beneficiaries. Once they have recognized its impact and have reflected on it, they may implement programs or seminars targeting and focusing at how the program can be utilized better in the academe. Also, they can come up with different activities that will help in assisting the beneficiaries in order to further enhance or improve the transformative powers of the program. Department of Social Welfare and Development. They be more aware of the perspective of parents regarding the 4Ps. Upon reflecting on the narratives of the participants, they can come up of several ways in order to further improve the delivery of the program towards its respective beneficiaries. They can tailor fit their topics for the monthly family development sessions that are aimed at helping the beneficiaries with their financial concerns. The school heads. They be more informed regarding

the status of the students under the 4Ps program. They could find ways in order to make sure that these beneficiaries are attending their classes and are active in their school. Also, through the findings of the study, they would design an information drive to help students in realizing the impact of 4Ps and how it could be used as a stepping stone in achieving their goals. The teachers. The teaches can design ways in order to keep the 4Ps student beneficiaries interested, included, and involved in their class. They can also design their instruction in a way that targets financial education. Moreover, they can also teach students life skills that they can use later on in life. This will help them become prepared in the future, whether or not they pursue higher education. Other stakeholders. Other stakeholders may provide avenue and opportunities for this student's beneficiaries. They can let them explore and discover ways to improve their well-being. Future researchers. The study contributes to their academic arsenal especially in the field of the transformative power of 4Ps. This shows how school and society is connected. They may conduct this study but taking on the students' perspective. As beneficiaries, they may have distinct opinions about how the program has affected their education.

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